

FILLING IN THE BLANKS: RETHINKING TERMS OF SERVICE THROUGH DESIGN

SEDA ÖZÇETİN

UMEÅ INSTITUTE OF DESIGN

SEDA.OZCETIN@UMU.SE

ABSTRACT

In this proposal to take part in Nordes doctoral consortium, I highlight Terms of Service (ToS) as a problematic contemporary concept to be explored in design for its role in structuring our relationships with fluid assemblages. I introduce my unfolding research program, aesthetics of relating, orientating towards concept of care based on a more-than-human worldview drawing from a variety of entanglement theories. Finally, I mention my short-term and long-term plans to achieve this research program.

INTRODUCTION

Advancements in digital technologies introduced not only new kinds of things, fluid assemblages – networked computational things – (Redström and Wiltse, 2018), but also new concepts such as artificial intelligence and machine learning, and familiar ones in new contexts such as Terms of Service (ToS), to our

everyday. ToS, a familiar legal concept encountered in user journey, is more than a touchpoint but a regulation mechanism structuring how people are supposed to form and sustain relations to and with fluid assemblages. Replacing ownership with ongoing relationships (Redström and Wiltse, 2018), ToS and its accompanying policies – the *ToSphere*¹, have dramatically changed how we relate to things, forcing us to go into legally binding agreements without reading, comprehending, and negotiating them.

While rooted in the legal domain, due to its complex character, *ToSphere* lends itself to a variety of disciplines resulting in the exploration of its core concepts such as privacy and consent in ethics, technical solutions such as coding privacy in computer science, alternative data governance models in business and economics, and its usability in human-computer interaction (HCI). However, these explorations seem to fail to account for *ToSphere* – what it is and does. Design, making the artifice and mediating our relation to it and the world as an affirmative act – proposing alternatives – (Dilnot, 2016) and with its ability to overview and fill in the blanks also by drawing from other disciplines might be better equipped for rethinking *ToSphere*.

Taking this challenge, as a PhD student at Umeå Institute of Design and DCODE², I conduct research on

1 I call the social ecosystem of distributed policies composed of ToS and its accompanying policies such as Privacy Policies, Cookies Policies, community guidelines, and several families of policies of third-party services, bounded by legal frameworks as General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), functioning as a shield around fluid assemblages, the *ToSphere*.

2 DCODE is an EU Horizon 2020 Marie Skłodowska-Curie Innovative Training Network (ITN). It is a consortium of seven

exceptional higher education institutions and stakeholders from industry, government, and civil society across Europe. Bringing together 40 researchers from 20 countries over four years, among them Technische Universiteit Delft, Københavns Universitet, Aarhus Universitet, Transport & Telecommunication Institute Lv, Stichting Hogeschool Van Amsterdam, Philips Electronics, and The University of Edinburgh, DCODE is set to rethink the digital transformation of society through 5 work packages, 'inclusive digital futures, trusted

ToSphere to create a shift from this non-negotiable contract model to a dynamic and negotiable social contract model that better distributes power and control (DCODE, 2021). Recognizing the agency of nonhumans – machines and artificial intelligence – in fluid assemblages for creating a more-than-human design worldview, I am engaging with critical posthumanism, object-oriented ontology, actor-network theory, co-performativity, to decenter the human and reveal the entanglements and power dynamics (Giaccardi and Redström, 2020; Forlano, 2017). In proposing alternatives for *ToSphere*, I am following programmatic research approach unfolding through design experiments (Redström, 2017). My research program, currently framed as aesthetics of relating, seems to be orientating towards the concept of ‘care’ on three pillars “labor/work, affect/affections, ethics/politics” (Puig de la Bellacasa 2017, 10). I intend to explore the dynamic relations with fluid assemblages through concepts such as temporality, agency and power in everyday negotiations as well as network therapy as a method to reveal and resolve conflicts, release tensions, and rehabilitate and rethink relations.

To achieve this research program, my short-term plans cover continued theoretical exploration through design experiments, mandatory activities at DCODE (winter and summer schools³, *prototeam*⁴, secondment⁵) and UID (courses⁶, dissertation⁷), and producing research outcomes individually and with my supervisors⁸, *prototeam*⁹, and fellow PhD students¹⁰. My long-term plans relate to becoming a unique and authentic design researcher embodying practices and processes with orientation as a feminist scholar creating poetic research

interactions, sustainable socio-economic models, democratic data governance, and future design practices’.

3 Summer and winter schools are twice-a-year occasions where DCODE ITN comes together for keynotes, workshops, and collaborative sessions. Each school is organized by one of the partner universities with a focus on the corresponding work package.

4 *Prototeam*, is an experimental team setting, where DCODE PhD students across 5 work packages come together to speculate on future design professions and practices in real-life contexts in collaboration with partners from industry, government, and civil society. The first round of *prototeams* took place in Spring 2022 semester. The second round will take place in Spring 2023 semester.

5 Secondment is an up to 3-month project requiring the PhD students to be stationed at one of the DCODE partner organizations. I will do my secondment at Advanced Care Research Center (ACRC) in Edinburgh, which would allow me to explore my care-centric approach in practical contexts.

through design portfolio fluidly moving in-between disciplinary boundaries.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work is part of the DCODE project. The project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955990. I would like to thank my supervisor Dr. Heather Wiltse, and my colleagues at UID Research Studio – Dr. Maria Göransdotter, Xaviera Sánchez de la Barquera Estrada, Anja Neidhardt, Pamela Gil-Salas, Ayşegül Özçelik, and Catharina Henje – for critically reviewing the work.

REFERENCES

- DCODE. 2021. Designing alternatives for the Terms of Service (ToS). [Online]. [Accessed 8 January 2023]. Available from: <https://dcode-network.eu/program/democratic-data-governance>
- Dilnot, C. 2016. In: Joost, G., Bredies, K., Christensen, M., Conradi, F., Unteidig, A. (eds.) *Design as research: positions, arguments, perspectives*. Basel: Birkhäuser. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783035607383>
- Forlano, L. 2017. Posthumanism and design. *She Ji The Journal of Design, Economics, and Innovation*. **3**(1), pp.16-29. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sheji.2017.08.001>
- Giaccardi, E. and Redström, J. 2020. Technology and more-than-human design. *Design Issues*. **36**(4), pp.33-44. Available from:

6 Remaining courses at UID: Design methodology, design ethics, ongoing research seminars, introduction to research ethics, writing science.

7 I plan to write a monograph and expect to have my %50 seminar in October 2023.

8 With my first supervisor Dr. Heather Wiltse, I am currently writing a paper for the Journal of Human-Computer Interaction’s special issue ‘Posthumanist HCI and the more-than-human turn in design’.

9 With my *prototeam*, I am currently working on two papers: (i) write up of the workshop ‘Sensing in the Wild’ that took place at DRS Labs 2022: Bilbao for the Labs publication, (ii) reflection on prototyping future design professions for ACM Transactions on Computer-Human Interaction (TOCHI) special issue on ‘Data/Algorithms/Models: prototyping with uncertainty in research through design’.

10 Further exploration of and reflections on ‘Urban Recipes’ project I co-designed with Yuxi Liu, PhD fellow at tuDelft and DCODE.

https://doi.org/10.1162/desi_a_00612

Puig de la Bellacasa, M. 2017. *Matters of care: speculative ethics in more than human worlds*. Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press.

Redström, J. 2017. *Making design theory*. Cambridge,

United States: MIT Press.

Redström, J. and Wiltse, H. 2018. *Changing things: the future of objects in a digital world*. London: Bloomsbury Visual Arts.